

FAMILY PERFORMANCE AND MENTAL HEALTH IN ADOLESCENTS

DESEMPEÑO FAMILIAR Y SALUD MENTAL EN ADOLESCENTES

RESUMEN

Esta investigación tuvo como objetivo explicar la salud mental basada en el desempeño familiar en adolescentes. Los instrumentos de investigación fueron el Cuestionario del Dispositivo de Evaluación Familiar (FAD) y el Cuestionario de la Escala de Depresión, Ansiedad y Estrés - 21 (DASS-21). Los resultados de la correlación de Pearson mostraron que existe una relación negativa significativa entre los aspectos de los componentes del desempeño familiar y la salud mental ($P < 0.01$). Además, los análisis de regresión múltiple mostraron que los aspectos de la resolución de problemas, la comunicación, la participación afectiva, el control del comportamiento y el rendimiento general fueron capaces de predecir la salud mental.

Palabras clave: Salud mental, desempeño familiar, dispositivo de evaluación familiar.

ABSTRACT

This research aimed to explain mental health based on family performance in adolescents. Research instruments were the Family Assessment Device (FAD) Questionnaire, and, Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale – 21 (DASS-21) questionnaire. The results of the Pearson correlation showed there is a negative significant relationship between the aspects of family performance components and mental health ($P < 0.01$). Moreover, multiple regression analyses showed that the aspects of problem-solving, communication, affective involvement, behavior control, and overall performance were able to predict mental health.

Keywords: mental health, family performance, Family Assessment Device

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INTRODUCTION

Mental Health is one of the most important principles in psychology and psychiatry that many researches have focused on this subject (Golchin, Nasiri, Najmiov & Bashardoost, 2018). Promoting mental health of the society, especially in effective and constructive generation, is required to the dynamism, maturity and advancement of that society (Noorbala, Bagheri fard & Yasami, 2014). Among the various age groups, adolescence students had considerable attention of researchers due to their unique features in their evolutionary period. Biological, cognitive, psychological and social processes undergo a remarkable alteration in teenage period. In this regard, some teens fail to adapt to these normal changes due to unusual pressure (Javadi, Aqabakhshi, Rafiei, Asgari, Memar & Abdizarrin, 2017). One of the major aspects of student's health is the mental health. Studies show that there is prevalence of mental disorders and mental diseases developing among students. Attention to mental health is important in all spheres of life, including personal, social and occupational lifetime. This is an integral part of normal and healthy personality which is related to family performance (Haddadi Kohsari, Rooshan & Asgharnazhad, 2018).

Family is one of the main determinants in improving the mental health. Family is one of the pillars of social life. In order to ensure that performing of main duties of the family in the best way, it must be constructed functionally effective (Dortaj and Mohammadi, 2016). Other researches demonstrate a negative correlation between family low performances and satisfaction of the basic needs of their children. Family performance is a common effort to establish and maintain a balance in the family (Hosseini and Samani, 2015).

The concept of family performance includes the quality of communication between family members and information about members' quest for promoting the quality of life. In fact, family performance refers to the ability of the family to perform its tasks, including providing for emotional, psychological, and physiological needs of members. Families with desirable performance have the features, such as the systematic distribution of roles, tasks, and assignments among all members, open communication interaction, control and management of psychological stress effectively, empathy, leadership, affection, and self-interest, and personal responsibility. Studies by several researchers suggested that there is a significant relationship between the poor performance of the family and the emergence of physical symptoms, anxiety, sleep disorders, depression and disturbance in social function among children (Fadakar Sogheh, Abbasi, Khaleghdoost & Atrkar Roshan, 2014.).

Khoshnam and Qamari (2017) in a study demonstrated a negative and significant relationship between the cognitive approach of coping with stress and impaired

family performance. There was a positive and significant relationship between emotional approach of coping with stress and impaired family performance. However, there was no significant relationship between avoidance and discouraging approach of coping with stress and family performance.

Diler, Birmaher, Axelson, Obreja, Monk, Hickey, Goldstein, Goldstein, Sakolsky, Iyengar, Brent & Kupfer (2017) concerning the role of family performance in mental health of students reported that with regard to the various responses that students receive from teachers, friends, family and parents, different judgments of other people and their perceptions of the reactions of others get into the permanent mindset. Ultimately students, by making a positive or negative self-concept may be individuals with a high self-esteem, determination and tolerant, optimistic and affectionate and perseverance towards affairs, or as insecure people with low self-confidence, bad, distressed and unbearable. All these personality traits that created during school years accrue to mental health or mental disorders.

Considering the above literature, family and its performance have attracted much attention recently. On the other hand, it is necessary to study due to the importance of the mental health of students, who have central role in progress of countries.

METHODS

The research is based on a descriptive study. The population of the study consisted of all high school girl students, who studied at high schools in Shiraz during 2016-2017. The sample of 150 high school students from Shiraz were selected by cluster sampling.

The Family Assessment Device (FAD)-60: The *FAD* questionnaire developed by Epstina, Baldwin and Bessibe in 1983 was used to assess the family function development (Sanei, 2015).

To collect the data, formal procedures were applied at the secondary school in Shiraz, to obtain the consent of both the participants and their parents. Next, the participants were instructed on the purpose of the study and its potential benefits. Also, they were given some instructions on how to fill the questionnaires. Then, the questionnaires were distributed among the participants by the researcher and they were asked to fill them. Finally, the researcher collected the questionnaires and rated them. Data analysis of the study was done by using SPSS software. At the inferential level, Pearson correlation coefficient tests and multiple regression analysis tests were employed to test the research hypotheses.

RESULTS

This section provides the descriptive indicators and the results of correlation and regression analysis to predict the mental health based on the subscales of developmental family performance variable as a predictor indicator. In table 1 descriptive variables are shown.

Table1. Descriptive statistics of variables

	Mean	SD	Max	Min
Problem solving	22.33	4.36	30	10
Relationship	25.34	4.42	35	15
Roles	33.49	5.18	45	21
Affective responsiveness	22.17	4.64	34	13
Affective involvement	26.61	4.27	35	15
Behavioral control	33.45	5.20	46	14
Main performance	51.42	9.64	65	17
Mental health	41.65	5.68	64	15

Resource: Authors, 2019

The results of the Pearson correlation test between criterion and predictor variables are shown in Table 2. As can be seen, there is a negative and significant relationship between the aspects of family performance and mental health.

Table 2. Pearson correlation between research variables

	Problem Solving	Relation ship	Roles	Affective Respon- siveness	Affective Involvement	Behavior al Control	Main Perform- ance	Mental Health
Problem solving	1							
Relationshi p	0.676**	1						
Roles	0.792**	0.582**	1					
Affective responsiveness	0.726**	0.709**	0.648**	1				
Affective involvement	0.747**	0.641**	0.708**	0.716**	1			
Behavioral control	0.533**	0.732**	0.608**	0.564**	0.638**	1		
Main performanc e	0.825**	0.775**	0.758**	0.824**	0.816**	0.737**	1	
Mental health	-0.392**	-0.316**	-0.382**	-0.286**	-0.298**	-0.150	-0.400**	1

Resource: Authors, 2019

Also, we used the regression analysis in order to determine the share of any of these dimensions. As shown in Table 3, the R value is 0.599 and the R² is 0.350. In other words, family performance explains 35% of the variance of mental health scores. Also, Aspects of problem solving, communication, emotional blend, behavioral control, and overall performance can predict mental health as negatively and significantly.

Table 3. The regression on the on predicting mental health based on family performance components

Criterion variable: Mental Health								
Predictor variable	R	R2	Df	F	P	B	t	P
Problem solving	0.599	0.350	149	13.546	0.001	-0.211	2.123	0.025
Relationship						-0.199	2.000	0.038
Roles						0.089	1.032	0.165
Affective responsiveness						-0.223	2.435	0.017
Affective involvement						0.129	1.765	0.089
Behavioral control						-0.254	2.879	0.009
Main performance						-0.311	3.134	0.001

Resource: Authors, 2019

DISCUSSION

The R value is 5.99 and the 2R ratio is 350. In other words, family function explains 35% of the variance of mental health scores. Also, dimensions of problem solving, communication, emotional blend, behavioral control, and overall performance can predict negative and significant mental health. Generally, Pearson's correlation test results show that there is a negative and significant relationship between mental health and all of family performance dimensions. In other words, with increasing family performance, the level of mental disorders decreases.

The results of present study are in line with Khoshnam and Ghamari (2017), who indicated that most human behaviors are dependent to several factors. As a result, the behavioral and psychological problems of adolescents and young individuals is no exception. They noted that the family, friends and cultural places (such as school), are the main factors determining the problematic behavior of adolescents and young people.

For instance, friends can affect and guide the adolescents toward problematic behavior at school and during their leisure time, and this time parent's encounter with the adolescent and the rituals of education that can enhance adolescent tendency toward friends, or that can prevent them.

In most studies, the largest share in determining the factors of behavior is dedicated to the family. It is maybe due to the fact that family is the first scholastic which a person experiences it, and the value and content of its education are directly related to the performance and content of the family environment. This performance not only includes factors such as the family's well-being and parenting education, but also consist of moral development of the family, how to communicate among members, suitability of the family's rules, roles share, problem solving, emotions expression, emotional needs supply, and so on.

In general, disorders or psychological problems of each person are the result of the pathological forms of family relationships. One of the most important factors in improving the mental health is the family. This system has a primary effect on people's lives and is effective in adapting them to the society and also in creating self-efficacy in adolescent children. Our study has cope with some limitations including, lack of control of other effective variables in the research, some of the predictor variables are correlated, which prevents more accurate analysis of the variables. Moreover, there was weak cooperation of the selected participants.

CONCLUSION

All in all, the results of this study confirm the main role of family performance in psychopathology. It can be said that one may predict mental health problems by studying people's understanding of the developmental family performance. It contributes to researchers' knowledge in understanding and treating mental problems.

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